

To Be or Not To Be

Developed by: Ryan North (gamebook)/Breadpig (publisher); Tin Man Games (digital)

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Keywords

Adaptation, Comedy, Critical Thinking, Discussion Skills, Drama, Gender Studies, Literary Studies, Queer Studies, Shakespeare, Tragedy

Figure 1. Image from *To Be or Not To Be* (Ryan North; Tin Man Games). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

The choose-your-own-adventure game *To Be or Not To Be* (see Figure 1) reimagines and remediates William Shakespeare's "Hamlet." The digital game was released in 2015 by the developer Tin Man Games, based on the gamebook by Ryan North (2013). It offers players the option to play as Hamlet, Ophelia, or King Hamlet, and manipulate events, thereby altering the narrative. The main objective is for players to experience alternative storylines through

their decisions as the game progresses. The game caters to a diverse audience by appealing to those interested in literature, comedy, and interactive storytelling. Thematic elements include fate versus free will, while the formal aspects encompass satire, parody, and the reinterpretation of classic literature through a modern, humorous lens (Bushnell, 2021; Novitz, 2020). Though not strictly designed as a serious game, “To Be or Not To Be” may be seen as combining educational content with entertainment, engaging users in active decision-making while also offering insights into the play’s structure and themes. The player reads text and selects options that influence the story’s direction.

Facts

Release date:	2013 (gamebook); 2015 (digital)
Developer:	Ryan North (gamebook)/Breadpig (publisher); Tin Man Games (digital)
Game type:	Analog, Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	At least 10 minutes, Optimal: c. 20–40 minutes. The duration depends on the choices made.
Languages:	English
Environment:	For the analog version, no requirements. The digital version is available on various platforms.
Material:	Shakespeare’s “Hamlet”. While in-depth knowledge of the play is not essential to enjoy the game, it does help enable more rounded, meaningful, and revealing interaction with what the game offers.
Price:	€4.99 (digital), on Steam; €22.41 (paperback) on Amazon.de

Resonance & Criticism

There has been increasing interest in the pedagogical usefulness of ‘Shakespeare games’ (Roberts-Smith & DeSouza-Coelho, 2021), sometimes used in educational settings to make Shakespeare’s work more accessible and engaging (Boyd, 2022). To Be or Not To Be also contributes to “a long history of adaptive performance” in the “popular and academic history of the Shakespeare network” (Harrison & Lutz, 2017). It blends interactive play with literature, thus offering a fresh approach to the text and having broad appeal. While the exact number of users is not public, the game has received mostly positive reviews, achieving a “Very Positive” rating on Steam (Steam, 2024) and “universal acclaim” on Metacritic. Similarly, critics praise its humor and creative narrative approach (Bushnell, 2021).

Game Principle & Process

As an interactive narrative, “To Be or Not To Be” allows players to “interact with embedded narratives to create new emergent narrative experiences” (Way, 2021) by playing as Hamlet,

Ophelia, or King Hamlet. Inspired by traditional “choose-your-own-adventure” books, the game’s mechanics involve reading modern, comedic rewrites of Shakespeare’s play—blending paraphrased lines, playful narration, and humorous asides—before making choices that affect the narrative’s path. By replacing Shakespeare’s Early Modern English with satirical, contemporary language, the text becomes more accessible while still referencing the original’s themes and iconic scenes. Players have considerable control over how the tale unfolds, with more than 100 possible endings.

The game’s objectives are clearly defined through the narrative, wherein players must overcome the challenges their chosen character faces (e.g., investigating the afterlife, avenging a death, or making scientific discoveries). The game uses a feedback method, reinforcing players’ choices with immediate narrative consequences. Rewards include new storylines, achievements, artwork, and replayability (Bushnell, 2021).

To Be or Not To Be offers a single-player experience. However, players are involved and engaged through dynamic conversations with in-game characters.

The game uses interactive storytelling to foster engagement, promoting critical thinking and a deeper understanding of Hamlet by enabling students to actively reshape the narrative, heightening their investment in and sense of “ownership” (Novitz, 2020) of the material.

Ryan North’s gamebook requires the reader/player to follow a set of rules to make sense of the story. Breaking the rules risks the narrative not making sense – which may even be the player’s goal. In this way, the gamebook paves the way for the video game to give players considerable control over the story’s events, encouraging deviation from the source text throughout the game.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Shakespeare is regularly taught in both literature and drama courses at higher education levels. By presenting multiple narrative paths, the game provides an alternative way of approaching the text and opens up debate on topics such as gender and character, decisions and turning points in tragedy (connecting with Rebecca Bushnell’s 2016 and 2021 work), and on stories untold and routes not taken. It also offers a way to broaden discussion to retellings of “Hamlet” in other media and genres, e.g., Tom Stoppard’s “Rosencrantz and Guildenstern Are Dead” or Ian McEwan’s “Nutshell”. It can sharpen critical reading skills, supplementing critical approaches, and can be applied to other literary/dramatic works. The game’s multiple storylines, centering different characters and plot junctions, highlight the play’s structure and directly engage with discussion topics that tend to arise in class, offering discussion prompts and encouraging student participation. The game may also be used in schools; however, the discussion topics and depth would vary across educational levels.

As Bushnell (2021) notes, the game “pit[s] the player against Shakespeare’s Hamlet” and thus lays the foundation for “both a critique of choice and character development”. For example,

following Shakespeare's choices as Ophelia (which deny Ophelia any agency) leads the narrator to tell the player off and shift the play to Hamlet's character (in a manner that Bushnell suggests invites the audience to think critically about expectations for tragedy). In this way, the game 'judges' the Shakespearean source itself and opens the play to further discussion.

For class use, teachers need only familiarize themselves with the game and ensure that students know something of the play. The teacher would then moderate the discussion. While class size could make a difference, one classroom practice could involve student discussions in small groups on individual experiences/playthroughs of the game, with the teacher guiding comparative discussion and integrating Shakespeare's play, thereby priming more searching discussion of "Hamlet". Though it is a single-player game, students can take turns making choices, shaping the narrative collaboratively; alternatively, they may vote for their preferred choice and be rewarded by the surprising outcomes, potentially prompting different angles on the play.

Effectiveness

As Roberts-Smith and DeSouza-Coelho (2021) note, Shakespeare games have the capacity to center "the act of playing pedagogically—that is, of interpreting and performing a text." Novitz (2020) argues that game adaptations like North's, in discouraging reverence, offer new ways of engaging with the play. The game has not been empirically evaluated as a pedagogical tool, but in our experience, students enjoy playing it in class, as evidenced by the enthusiastic response and feedback. Accessible to players of various skill levels, it provides an opportunity for participatory engagement. Shared knowledge of the play may lead to collective surprise and laughter, making it a memorable communal learning experience.

Pedagogically, *To Be or Not To Be* works best when approached with foreknowledge of "Hamlet" for a better appreciation of the play's playful, parodic, and critical engagement with the material. It stimulates critical discussion of the play by encouraging, and sometimes forcing, departures from Shakespeare's plot. The humor's effectiveness, the scope of comparative discussion, and the critical angles produced by this divergence are enhanced by knowledge of the text.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game is only available in English and features mature themes, such as death, which echo Shakespeare's source work.

In broader discussions of the educational uses of digital Shakespeares, Casey (2019) cautions that excessive reliance on digital resources may favor superficial readings of Shakespeare. However, Boyd (2022) notes that Casey's view tends to underestimate the creativity of digital approaches and their pedagogical potential. By prompting the unpacking of issues dramatized in *Hamlet*, this game supports the development of well-rounded perspectives by engaging

students' broader interest in games and fostering reciprocal understanding between *To Be or Not to Be* and Shakespeare's play.

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